

Sustainable Urban Development in economically important cities of Kerala: Ecological Restoration and Pollution Mitigation

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Abstract:

This paper reports sustainable urban development especially ecological restoration and pollution mitigation strategies in economically important cities Thiruvananthapuram and Kochi, Kerala, India. The research article highlights the importance of a participatory approach, municipal solid waste management, integrated planning, and landscape ecological methods for urban and wetland restoration. A mixed method approach has been suggested, covering qualitative case studies and quantitative data analysis. The key issues such as poor water quality, loss of biodiversity, and increase of pollution in the study area were identified through preliminary investigation. The paper also highlights municipal solid waste management and government initiatives such as the Ashtamudi lake restoration and the Kochi solar power system. These examples show the possible probabilities towards sustainable urban development and the effectiveness of community engagement, decentralized waste management, and renewable energy adoption.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Thiruvananthapuram, Kochi, mixed method approach, community planning

1. Introduction:

Kerala, known for its lush landscapes and intricate waterways, faces significant challenges as urbanization encroaches upon its natural resources. The freshwater system plays a major role in determining the well-being of humans as well as living things on the earth. Rapid urbanization and industrialization have led to increased pressure on land, water, and energy resources in Kerala (Chaithanya et al., 2017). The government of Kerala has intervened many times by implementing policies and regulations to restrict the use of land, such as the Land Ceiling Act of 1963. However, despite these efforts, the development pattern in Kerala, often referred to as the "Kerala Model", is unique compared to other parts

of the country. Instead of relying on the primary or secondary sectors, the tertiary sector has played a significant role in Kerala's development model. This steady increase in urbanization in Kerala, accompanied by slow overall development, is a matter of concern that requires attention from researchers, planners, and policymakers. The geographical development in Kerala has resulted in a network of small towns that have formed an urban expanse without a primate city. This unique urban landscape poses both environmental and social challenges for Kerala. One of the major environmental challenges faced by Kerala is ecological degradation (Lal & Nair, 2017). This degradation is caused by deforestation, pollution of water bodies, and habitat destruction. The increasing pollution levels and degradation of natural resources have led to a rise in epidemic diseases such as cholera, dengue fever, and malaria. Additionally, the rapid growth of industries and urban settlements has resulted in significant environmental pollution, further impacting the sustainability of Kerala's model of development (Thimm, 2017). Given these challenges, it is imperative to prioritize sustainable urban development in Kerala. Sustainable development aims to address the environmental, social, and economic aspects of urbanization while ensuring the preservation and enhancement of natural resources for future generations. By adopting sustainable practices, Kerala can mitigate pollution, restore ecological balance, and promote economic growth that is equitable and environmentally conscious.

The literature studies revealed the importance of sustainable urban development, ecological restoration, and pollution mitigation. The literatures also examine case studies from around the world, drawing parallels and contrasts with the situation in Kerala. Srikumar published an article on methodological discourse for urban river restoration. The author explained the concept with two examples from Kerala. The author argued that a participatory approach could be an alternative to the co-revolutionary framework under the river restoration (Chattopadhyay, 2022). Sunil Kumar and his colleague reported on integrated planning for sustainable development of the Kuttanad wetland region. The paper revealed the present situation of wetlands in Kerala as well as globally. The authors also recommended a possible approach to sustainable planning. In light of climate change and increased awareness about sustainability, one can utilize planning as a tool to integrate 'aspirations for growth' as a decisive measure for the planning of cities and analyze it utilizing existing mechanisms for planning without suggesting a drastic overhaul of the existing system (Kumar & Devadas, 2016). Surya published a research paper on landscape ecological urban marsh land restoration. The paper briefly outlined the process for the restoration of marsh land located in Chennai.

Principles of landscape ecology, landscape, and ecological urbanism, are also discussed in that paper. Advanced software and imaging techniques were used to arrive at the outline for marsh land restoration process(Surya, 2016). Ecosystem restoration provides not only a healthy environment but also sustainability and resilient development (Gupta et al., 2023). Sheela et al. studied the water quality and land pattern for sustainable developments needed in coastal urban areas. The study reported that the Thiruvananthapuram city is mainly responsible for pollution in land, and water bodies(Sheela et al., 2014). To mitigate or prevent pollution, the following techniques such as sewage treatment in houses, hotels, hospitals, and municipal solid dumping areas are some of the best options for developing countries. Sinclair et al. published a book chapter on sustainable management of wetlands and assessment of ecosystem restoration services(Sinclair et al., 2020). Vijay Jain et al published a book chapter on ecosystem restoration (Jain et al., 2023). They discussed the scientific aspects of policy development in ecosystem restoration. The study emphasized the importance of eco-restoration of wetlands, urban ecosystems, and Himalayan regions towards the enhancement of biodiversity. Further, the study supports the other important strategies and stakeholder involvement to attain sustainability, especially during the 2021–2030 decade of ecosystem restoration. The book chapter specifically emphasized policy-making in ecological restoration.Viju Nambiar and Mohammed investigated the impact of urbanization on the metropolitan region of Malapuram in detail. They used satellite images and NDVI assessments to study ecosystem degradation. The study revealed that agricultural land has been converted to buildings, resulting in increased ecosystem degradation and increased disaster vulnerability. They advocate for participatory sustainable land management to mitigate these impacts, offering both general and specific planning recommendations to address the ongoing challenges of land degradation and promote sustainable regional development(Viju et al., 2023).Geeta Mehta et al. emphasized the impact of urbanization on the degradation of river water quality. The river water has been seriously damaged mainly by urbanization. The study discussed the solutions must extend beyond river channels, considering entire ecosystems including tributaries and groundwater. The piece critiques rapid urbanization and agricultural practices for diminishing river health and disrupting hydrological balance. It promotes nature-based infrastructure and decentralized, community-led efforts as sustainable, long-term solutions. The review ultimately calls for comprehensive stakeholder cooperation to halt degradation and commit to the prolonged process of river restoration(Mehta & Jade, 2024).Kiran Kumar S et al discussed the "Resilience Master Plan" as a strategic approach to actualize sustainable development goals in Kozhikode, Kerala,

India. The study explores the dichotomy between urbanization's benefits and its inherent vulnerabilities, especially in the face of disasters and climate change. The paper discusses that while urban centers have thrived, they have also become increasingly susceptible to various threats. It presents resilience as a critical characteristic, enabling cities to withstand and recover from adversities, thereby acting as a pathway to sustainability. The study assesses Kozhikode's current master plan, proposing ways to enhance the city's resilience and achieve sustainable development systematically (Kumar S & C.A, 2022). The literature titled "Restoration, Construction, and Conservation of Degrading Wetlands" focuses on the critical role of wetlands in mitigating various water-related issues, particularly in developing economies plagued by pollution, resource demand, and population growth. It critiques the inadequacy of traditional and advanced wastewater treatment technologies in these regions due to cost and effectiveness constraints. The review advocates for the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of natural wetlands as a cost-effective, manageable solution for water purification, emphasizing their importance for achieving a sustainable environment. The chapter calls for a paradigm shift towards natural wetland conservation as a crucial step in sustainable management practices (Suhani et al., 2020).

Literature studies emphasize the importance of participatory approaches, integrated planning, and landscape ecological methods for urban and wetland restoration. Studies highlight the need for sustainable management of resources and ecosystems, particularly in light of the rapid conversion of agricultural land to urban areas and the deteriorating water quality due to urbanization. Collectively, these studies support a comprehensive and participatory approach to mitigate environmental degradation, enhance resilience, and promote sustainable growth in Kerala.

2. Methodology:

The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data analysis with qualitative case studies and interviews with policymakers, urban planners, and local communities. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of various sustainable development initiatives.

2.1 Study area

Trivandrum is an important commercial and industrial city in the state of Kerala. The city has tourism, a hospital, and the world's best educational institute. Similarly, Kochi is also an important commercial industrial city in the state of Kerala. The city is classified as tier II city

by Indian government. Kochi is also known as the queen of the Arabian Sea and one of the important spice trading hub in the world. The urbanization rate has increased by about 80 percent in these two cities with employment patterns and income sources. Most of the urbanization developed in an unplanned manner, especially in the study areas. These two major cities need to have efficient sustainable plans immediately for future urban development as the fresh water system, soil, and air have been polluted due to urbanization and anthropogenic activities. The following areas with distinct topographical features were studied.

(a) Study area for determination of BOD and other physicochemical parameters of water sample: Sampling site at Trivandrum:- Karamana River (KR1), Jagathi River (JR2), Amayizhanchan River (AR3), Killi River (KR4). Sampling site at Kochi:- Periyar (Manakkakadavu) MK1, Chithirapuzha (CP2), Kadubrayer (KB3), Unthithode (UT4).

(b) Study area for determination of Microbial and organic contaminants in soil, Trivandrum: Vilappilsala, Pazhavangadi, Kunchalammoodu, and Kochi (Municipal waste disposal area).

(c) Determination of Air pollution – sampling site in Trivandrum as follows, Kazhakottam (KK), Valiyathura (VT), Veli (V), East fort (EF) sampling site in Kochi as follows, Vyttila (VY), Kodavautte (KV), Kathirikadavu (KK), Athirapalli (AP)

3. Key issues in the study areas of Trivandrum and Kochi

The author conducted various studies such as physicochemical analysis of water, soil, and air in the study areas. The physicochemical analysis was conducted from January 2019 to September 2022 as the primary study and based on the results obtained the major key issues are as follows:

- ❖ The pH, salinity, and hardness of water do not meet the standard of drinking water quality.
- ❖ Reduction in fish population, decrease in waterways and increase in pest and microplastic content has been observed.
- ❖ Increase in disease and chemicals in water and soil.
- ❖ Scarcity in drinking water and poor solid waste as well as improper management of waste has been found as key issues in the selected study areas.
- ❖ Air pollution

After identification of the problems, the results were arrived at through standard physicochemical analytical protocol, interview with people; expert discussion, and literature review, the root cause for the problems was listed based on the ranking method. The causes of the issues are as follows, poor waste management, poor integrated planning, clogged water, poor agricultural practices, excessive tourism, building construction, population increases, and commercialization.

4. Pollution Mitigation Strategies:

The pollution mitigation methods include waste management systems, the adoption of renewable energy, and green transportation. Urbanization increases day by day, which leads to creating a lot of pollution with detrimental effects on human health.

Waste Management Systems - Efficient waste segregation units decentralized waste management systems and recycling, and reuse practices would help to mitigate pollution.

Renewable Energy Adoption – Renewable energy sources including solar power systems have emerged with a lot of applications. The government has offered incentives to install solar power systems. The use of solar power is not only efficient but also mitigates pollution effectively.

Green transportation – The role of green transportation is very important in the sustainable development of the ecosystem. The government has invested in public infrastructure transport, electric vehicles, pedestrian pathways, and cycling lanes. These initiatives would reduce vehicle emissions and enhance eco-friendly commuting habits. Advanced technology towards green transportation is highly recommended to improve efficiency as well as to promote eco-friendly nature. Additionally, the research sheds light on the challenges faced in the implementation process, including technological barriers, policy gaps, and societal resistance. Eventually, green transportation and integrated approaches address the complicated challenges associated with urban pollution.

5. Case Studies:

Several case studies are presented to illustrate the practical application of sustainable urban development practices in Kerala. These may include the rejuvenation of the Ashtamudi Lake, the Alappuzha waste management model, and Kochi's solar-powered initiatives.

Ashtamudi Lake restoration:

Ashtamudi Lake, one of the largest estuarine ecosystems in Kerala, faced significant degradation due to pollution and unsustainable practices. The rejuvenation project undertaken by the Kerala State Pollution Control Board (KSPCB) and local authorities aimed to restore the ecological balance of the lake.

a. **Integrated Solid Waste Management:** The project incorporated an efficient waste management system, reducing the inflow of solid waste into the lake. This involved community awareness programs, waste segregation at source, and the establishment of waste treatment facilities.

b. **Biodiversity Conservation:** Initiatives were implemented to protect and restore the biodiversity of the lake, including the plantation of native species, removal of invasive species, and the creation of buffer zones to prevent encroachment.

c. **Water Quality Improvement:** Collaborative efforts were made to control industrial effluents and sewage discharge into the lake. Water quality monitoring systems were put in place, ensuring continuous assessment and prompt action against any pollutant sources.

Alappuzha Waste Management Model:

Alappuzha often termed the 'Venice of the East,' gained recognition for its innovative waste management practices.

a. **Community Engagement:** A key feature of the Alappuzha model was the active involvement of the local community. Residents participated in waste segregation, composting, and recycling initiatives, reducing the burden on landfills.

b. **Decentralized Composting Units:** The city established decentralized composting units to process organic waste locally. This not only reduced transportation costs but also produced nutrient-rich compost for agricultural use.

c. **Plastic Ban and Alternatives:** Alappuzha implemented a strict ban on single-use plastics and promoted the use of eco-friendly alternatives. This significantly curtailed plastic pollution and enhanced the overall environmental sustainability of the region.

Kochi's Solar-Powered Initiatives:

Kochi, a major urban center in Kerala, exemplifies the integration of renewable energy sources for sustainable urban development.

- a. **Solar Power in Public Spaces:** The city has embraced solar energy in public spaces, with solar panels installed on government buildings, streetlights, and public transport systems. This initiative has not only reduced the city's carbon footprint but also lowered energy costs.
- b. **Smart Infrastructure:** Kochi implemented smart infrastructure solutions powered by solar energy, including solar-powered traffic signals and surveillance systems. These initiatives enhance efficiency while minimizing the environmental impact.
- c. **Green Building Practices:** Kochi has witnessed a surge in green building practices, with an emphasis on sustainable architecture and energy-efficient construction. This has contributed to the city's overall resilience to climate change and reduced reliance on traditional energy sources.

Sustainable solid waste management in urban areas

Municipal solid waste management - Solapur city, Maharashtra, India: The municipal solid waste management in Solapur City was investigated by Chavan and his colleague. The study includes the following key aspects such as generation of waste, transportation, treatment and disposal of waste. The study concludes that the existing solid waste management ((Management and Handling) Rules, 2000) have several lacunas(Thakare et al., 2018).

Municipal solid waste management Asturias, Spain: Lifecycle assessment (LCA) application to sustainable municipal solid waste management has been rapidly developed and employed in complicated systems of solid waste management. The municipal solid waste generated in Asturias was managed by six strategies, namely landfill recovery of biogas, direct incineration with energy recovery, biomethanization from organic waste fraction, aerobic stabilization of organic fraction, biomethanization of the source-separated organic fraction, sorting of the mixed fraction and landfill of the rejected following aerobic stabilization of the organic fraction(Fernández-Nava et al., 2014). The impact on ecosystem quality, human health, global warming, and resource depletion was also considered during the evaluation. The study concluded that, in the LCA process, scenario 3 i.e. biomethanization of the source from organic waste and incineration of rejected fraction has the least impact on the ecosystem while the scenarios including land filling produce the greatest impact on the environment.

6. Challenges and Opportunities:

The preliminary study was conducted that is the assessment of pollutants in water, air, and soil in urban areas of Kochi and Thiruvananthapuram in the state of Kerala, India. The preliminary study includes detailed physicochemical analysis such as pH, BOD, electrical conductance, TDS, organic pollution, microplastics, and microbial content. The experimental data highlighted that the ecosystem (soil, water, air) has deteriorated due to urbanization and industrialization. Based on the preliminary analysis, pollution control, resource management, and policy implementation are challenging. The opportunities are novel pollution management techniques, sustainable urban planning, research and development, and policy recommendations. The policy recommendation can be prepared for environmental problems.

Enhanced Monitoring and Regulation: Implement stricter monitoring of industrial activities and urban development to reduce pollution.

Sustainable Urban Planning: Integrate sustainable practices in urban planning to mitigate environmental impacts.

Pollution Remediation Programs: Develop programs for the remediation of contaminated water and soil.

Public Awareness and Education: Increase public awareness and education on environmental issues and sustainable practices.

Investment in Research and Development: Encourage research in pollution control and sustainable resource management.

Collaboration with Environmental Experts: Engage with environmental scientists and experts in policy formulation and implementation.

These recommendations are aimed at creating a balance between urban development and environmental sustainability in Kerala.

7. Problem identification strategies

The following approaches should be considered for problem identification in the study area which includes, comparative analysis, trend analysis, geographical analysis, correlation analysis, source identification, impact assessment, and regulatory compliance. The following figure expands on the key points of problem identification.

These strategies can help in systematically identifying and understanding the problem areas, which is a crucial step in developing effective solutions for pollution control and environmental restorations.

8. Integrated approach for problem solving

The key points for the integrated planning approach are as follows, data-driven decision-making, universal approach, Community Engagement and Education, Policy Development, sustainable development, regular monitoring, and adaptation. The detailed flow chart is presented in the following figure.

This integrated approach would effectively mitigate the environmental problems that arise due to urbanization in the study region of Kochi, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. The integrated planning approach highlighted here is based on the guidelines of government departments, members of the concerned planning agency, and literature. The planning process is proposed for two years and suggested one additional year for the vetting process. The later stage can be expanded for public discussion.

9. Conclusion:

The article highlights the need for sustainable urban development to address the challenges faced by Kochi and Thiruvananthapuram. The preliminary finding reveals that the water, air and soil have been polluted due to rapid urbanization and poor waste management systems. The study underscores the importance of integrated sustainable urban planning, aiming to control pollution, resource management, and community engagement. Strict regulation of urban development and monitoring of industrial activities are highly insisted upon. The article also highlights the importance of environmental education and public awareness. The novel techniques in decentralized waste management, renewable energy usage, and green transportation would help for successive sustainable urban development. The case studies both in Kerala as well as globally show exemplars for positive sustainable urban development in the long term. The paper concludes by insisting on the requirement for collaboration with environmental scientists in policy formulation and implementation of sustainable

development to achieve a balance between urban development and environmental conservation in Thiruvananthapuram and Kochi, Kerala.

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